

The Chinese Christian scroll Pelliot chinois 3847

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Entry tags: Syriac Text, Religious Group, Abrahamic, Literary Chinese, Text, Christian, Language, Eastern Christianity, Classical-Middle-Modern Sinitic, Sino-Tibetan, Sinitic, Church of the East (East Syriac)

The small, six-sheet Christian scroll, known by its modern pressmark Pelliot chinois 3847, was discovered in the famous Library Cave near Dunhuang. Since its in situ acquisition by Paul Pelliot (1878-1945) in 1908, the provenance of this scroll has been well documented. The first published description of the scroll was made in 1909 by Luo Zhenyu 羅振玉 (1866-1940) in his *Dunhuang shishi yishu* 敦煌石室遺書 (Lost Books from the Dunhuang Stone Chamber). The next year, Luo published five facsimiles of the texts of the scroll in *Shishi bibao* 石室秘寶 (Secret Treasures from the Stone Chamber). Housed in the Bibliothèque nationale de France, both the texts and materiality of the scroll provide important witnesses to Christianity in Tang China (618-907) and likely through to the time of the Library Cave's sealing in the early eleventh century. Of such witnesses, A.C. Moule recognized the scroll's content as being second in importance only to that of the Xi'an Stele of 781. Recent scholarship has favored dating the production of this scroll to after the Tang and before the cave's sealing, though the composition of at least some of its texts likely date to during the Tang. The scroll contains three distinct texts. The first is titled *Daqin Jingjiao sanwei mengdu zan* 大秦景教三威蒙度讚 (Hymn in Praise of the Salvation Achieved through the Three Majesties of the Luminous Teaching), and is a Chinese translation, in metrical form, of the *Gloria in excelsis Deo*. The hymn remains the only text of the so-called *Jingjiao* corpus to be a complete translation of a known Christian work. The second text is simply titled *Zunjing* 尊經 (the Scripture of the Honored) – note that 'scripture' (*jing*) here possesses a wider semantic range than just canonized Christian Scriptures. This work begins with an invocation to the Trinity and is followed by a list of honored persons and texts. Some of the Chinese names are transcriptions of foreign words – likely Syriac, in most cases. The third text is a postscript supplying an historical narrative on the translation of Christian works into Chinese. This narrative supplies information that both parallels and complements the Xi'an Stele. The note likely points to the titles listed in the *Zunjing* as those of Christian works then existing in Chinese. The note also provides rare information on the original materiality of Christian books before the translation of some of their texts onto scrolls. Regarding material aspects of the scroll itself, red reader's marks in the hymn text suggest this copy was once used for liturgy. The scroll also evidences being assembled piecemeal, with texts written onto sheets before later being joined to form a single scroll. At the end of the scroll, a red seal with seal characters for *Daqin si* 大秦寺, denoting a Christian monastery or church, again suggests this text was used by Christians before entering the predominantly Buddhist context of the Mogao Caves 莫高窟.

Date Range: 635 CE - 1000 CE

Region: Christianity Under Tang Rule (c. 700 CE)

Region tags: East Asia, China, Central Asia, Chang'an, China, Xi'an 西安, Luoyang, Dunhuang

At least for now, evidence written in Chinese for Christianity in Tang China largely comes from Chang'an, Luoyang, and Dunhuang. These were also prominent places along the so-called Silk Roads. For a time, Christian communities further west of Dunhuang (in an area often generally referenced in

Chinese texts as the Western Regions (西域) also came under Tang rule.

Status of Readership:

- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Luo Zhenyu 羅振玉 1909. Dunhuang shishi yishu 敦煌石室遺書. Songfenshi.
- Source 2: Luo Zhenyu 羅振玉 1910. Shishi bibao 石室秘寶. Shanghai.
- Source 1: Lin Wushu 林悟殊 2003. Tangdai Jingjiao zai yanjiu 唐代景教再研究. Beijing: Zhongguo shehui kexue chubanshe.
- Source 2: Wu Qiyu 吳其昱 1986. Jingjiao sanwei mengdu zan yanjiu 景教三威蒙度讚研究. Bulletin of the Institute of History and Philology, Academia Sinica 57/3, 411-438.
- Source 3: Lin Lijuan 林麗娟 2020. On the Transmission of the Gloria in excelsis Deo: Daqin jingjiao sanwei mengdu zan 大秦景教三威蒙度讚. In Shabo Talay ed., Überleben im Schatten : Geschichte und Kultur des syrischen Christentums. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz, 111-132.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://iranicaonline.org/articles/christianity-iii>
- Source 1 Description: A concise entry by Nicholas Sims-Williams on the early spread of Christianity to Central Asia.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/btv1b8303183c.image>
- Source 1 Description: Digitized images from the Bibliothèque nationale de France of the text-side of the scroll.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Written

Inked

- with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

– Specify: Mulberry

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Based on glue residue evident over some of the writing (along with other evidence), individual texts as well as portions of text were first written on sheets of paper (some individual sheets and others joined) before later all being joined to form this scroll.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: No other copies of the Chinese texts for the Gloria hymn or the Zunjing are known to exist so it is uncertain whether there were modifications to the texts in this scroll.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb

– No

↳ Cemetery

– No

↳ Temple

– No

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker

– No

↳ Cenotaph

– No

Notes: The adjacent Cave 16 honors the Buddhist monk Hongbian.

↳ Church

– Field doesn't know

Notes: An apparent stamp of ownership, at the end the scroll, suggests that it was once used in a Christian church or monastery.

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– Yes

Notes: It was found in one of the Mogao caves near Dunhuang. This particular cave, the famous Library Cave, was sealed in sometime in the early eleventh century and was only discovered at the turn of the twentieth century.

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– Field doesn't know

↳ Library/archive

– Field doesn't know

↳ Specify

– Specify: The purpose of Cave 17 (i.e. the so-called Library Cave) remains undetermined.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Notes: There are no accompanying images or iconography known for this scroll, though a damaged Christian painting, likely of a Christian saint, was also found in the Library Cave.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– No

Notes: Some of the titles in the Zunjing are Chinese transcriptions of foreign names (most likely came from Syriac) of written works and persons.

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

Notes: The texts are in Classical (or Literary) Chinese and contain a number of specialized terms borrowed from Chinese Buddhist or other domestic traditions.

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Other [specify]: At present, there is no conclusive evidence specifying the Chinese language as a sacred language within Christianity. For these Christians in China, Syriac was likely the language of liturgy, though some scholars believe that the Christian Syriac liturgy was eventually translated into Chinese.

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– I don't know

Notes: Paralleling information in the Xi'an Stele of 781, the postscript's recounting of the arrival of the Christian Aluoben to the Tang court in 635 may have been part of a wider Chinese Christian oral tradition preserving his story, though this remains uncertain.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Notes: Red reader's marks present in the first text (the Gloria hymn) suggest this text was read aloud, possibly as part of the liturgy.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– No

Notes: Religious professionals are not singled out by the text of this version of the Gloria hymn, which includes mention of proselytization.

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– No

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?

– No

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– No

Notes: The Zunjing does not explicitly contain content related to proselytization, though the postscript does recount the task to translate Christian writings into Chinese, which would presumably be a part of proselytization efforts.

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

↳ Is it orally recited?

– I don't know

Notes: Red reader's marks in the Gloria hymn, suggest that it was read aloud, though whether it was orally recited remains uncertain.

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?
 - Specify: The Gloria hymn was an important part of the East Syriac Christian liturgy.
- ↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ How often do the rituals take place?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices?
 - No
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?
 - No
- ↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?
 - Yes
 - Notes: If the Gloria hymn text was used in liturgy, then bread and wine would have been consumed as part of the liturgy.

Is there material significance to the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is it visible?

– Yes

Notes: Presumably before it was stored in the Library Cave.

↳ Is it hidden?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unknown why this Christian scroll found its way into the Library Cave.

↳ Can it be touched?

– Yes

↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?

– No

↳ Does the text serve a protective function?

– No

↳ Does the text serve a healing function?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?

– No

↳ Does the text serve as an incantation?

– No

↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Specify: The manuscript shows signs of coming together piecemeal. The sheets containing the hymn portion of P.3847 appear to have once been separate from the Zunjing text and its postscript. The "endleaves" of the scroll are both shorter sheets that seem to have been added later, though it is unclear how much later.

↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?

– No

↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?

– No

↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?

Please specify the substances in the sub-questions

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– I don't know

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– I don't know

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: It would have been part of the liturgy.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– Field doesn't know

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– No

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: This hymn is part of the liturgical tradition.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Bibliography

Notes: For the Zunjing text, Christian works translated into Chinese are listed followed with an explanatory postscript.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: This is not explicit, though it is certainly implied.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarh (king=high god)

– No

- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
 - Yes
- ↳ Other features of the supreme high god
 - Specify: Mighty, Merciful, Unchanging
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - Yes
 - Notes: In the text, God's knowledge of humanity is expressed via his acknowledging humanity's need for salvation. Thus, in the short text of the hymn, God's knowledge of this world is expressed in a general way.
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Notes: This is not specified in the text.

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Notes: The text seems to indirectly address this by God's knowing the spiritual need of humanity.

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– No

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

Notes: This is not specifically addressed in the hymn text.

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Can reward

– Yes

↳ Can punish

– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– No

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– No

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: Supreme ruler of all

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– No

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– Yes

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?

– Yes

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?

– No

↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?

– No

↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?

– Yes

- ↳ What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).
 - Yes

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

Notes: With the exception of the Messiah who came in human form.

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– No

- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– No

- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: The devil is simply mentioned without further elaboration.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: Regarding supernatural beings, only the Trinity and the devil are mentioned in the hymn text.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: no

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– No

Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

Supernatural being care about taboos

– No

Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

Notes: General worship of the Christian Trinity is encouraged in the hymn text and is also modeled in the first part of the Zunjing text.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: The faithful will be saved by God from the devil.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: God is presented as the ruler of all, but there is no explicit mention of punishment.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

Notes: In the text, Jesus the Messiah is the one that brings forth God's mercy.

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– I don't know

Notes: The hymn text leaves the prerogative for meting out salvation with God, though the text itself also includes a request that God be merciful.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– No

Notes: The text mentions God's salvation in a way that does not specify timeframes, though the text could also be read as including the afterlife given its mention of the eternal God.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?

– Yes

↳ Consists of good luck?

– No

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– No

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– No

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– No

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: Peace on earth and life eternal

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified

– Yes

↳ Coming in this lifetime

– Yes

↳ Coming on a specified date

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future

– No

Notes: The Second Coming of the Messiah is not specified in this text, though it is in other Christian texts, including extant East Syriac Chinese texts.

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future

– No

Notes: The Messiah's Second Coming is not mentioned in this text.

↳ Coming has already passed

– Yes

Notes: This is as regards Jesus the Messiah's first coming.

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– No

Notes: In the hymn, the Son (Jesus the Messiah) sits on a throne at the right hand of his Father, though the text itself does not explicitly touch on earthly politics.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– No

Other purpose

–Specify: He takes away the sins of the world.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Notes: It is not explicitly mentioned.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– I don't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is universal?

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is widespread?

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: Clergy – possibly, Jingjing himself, likely produced this Chinese version of the Gloria hymn.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Clergy were likely responsible for the transmission of this text, though this is not certain in this particular case.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– An empire

Notes: The imperially initiated Huichang Persecution (840s) may have resulted in the destruction of Christian texts, though the particulars remain unclear.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

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